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Routledge, 1997

the most important contact language is Arabic
borrowings also from French

1. Phonotactics

- boundary glosses:
- joins morphemes
 - joins part of compound verbs
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- all plosives, fricatives, nasals, liquids, glides occur word-, syllable- and morpheme-initially
 - all plosives, fricatives, nasals, liquids, glides occur word-, syllable- and morpheme-medially
 - all plosives, fricatives, nasals, liquids, glides occur word-, syllable- and morpheme-finally
 - voiceless plosives /p, t, tʃ, k/ aspirated in syllable initial position, unaspirated syllable finally
 - [ʔ] is never phonologically distinctive in word initial position, only distinctive in non-initial position (though final ʔ is prone to deletion)
 - ex.: no 'new'
 - noʔ 'kind, sort'
 - /q/ has several realizations: [G, ɣ, q] - [ɣ] never word-initially
 - word final /v/ can only be preceded by /a/ or /i/
 - ex.: gav 'cow'
 - div 'devil'
 - clusters:
 - no word-initial C-clusters
 - borrowed words with an initial cluster are broken up with a V:
 - via prothesis: V inserted before cluster -> VC.C
esport 'sport'
 - via anaptyxis: V inserted between Cs -> CV.C
færanse 'France'
 - medially: clusters are permitted in monomorphemic words
many other cluster result at the juncture of morphemes with as

many as three Cs contiguously, but there is a syllable boundary after the first two Cs and before the third C

often: reduction of clusters

ex.: bæxʃ.namɛ 'circular'

- syllable finally: clusters of 2 consonants are allowed
- geminates: occur typically in words of arabic origin, phonologically distinctive
ex.: bæna 'building, base'
bænna 'mason, construction worker'
 - only phonetically realized as long C when followed by a V (domain: stem+suffix)
ex.: /rædd/ [ræd] --ʒod (compound verb)
rejection became
'he failed'
[rædd]-e piʒnɛhad
rejection-EZ proposal
'rejection of the proposal'
- geminate in Persian-origin words are often the results of assimilation (see: assimilatory processes), if not then they are often reduced
- diphthongs:
 - phonemic status unclear
 - allow only 1 following C within a syllable (short V can be followed by 2 C)
- V-sequences:
 - /a/ + /e/ cannot occur within a word
 - many sequences result from sequences of a lexical morpheme plus either an inflectional or derivational morpheme, but intramorphemic sequences exist also
ex.: ziba-i
beautiful-ATTR 'beauty'
xiar 'cucumber'
 - when 2 contiguous Vs belonging to separate morphemes conjoin depending on phonetic environment, either a [y], [h] or nothing is inserted between them, or one of the V is dropped (domain: stem -suffix)

2. Syllable Structure

- (?)V, (?)VC, (?)VCC, CV, CVC, CVCC
- (?) - glottal stop insertion word initially, see: insertion rule
- canonical syllable type for words on citation form or breath group initially: CV(C) (C), where the first C is an epenthetic glottal stop when the syllable starts with a V
- ex.: /e.te.faq/ 'experience'
/al.mas/ 'diamond'

/æsb/ 'horse'

/pɔft/ 'behind'

- syllabification rule: boundary before every CV-sequence
dæ.mɑq 'nose'
ɛf.kəl'dɪfɪkəl'ti 'difficulty'
- no non-vowel syllabics

3. Vowel Harmony

- restricted phenomenon
- involve a few prepositions, clitics, inflections
- applies across morpheme boundary: involves a lexical root which triggers a change either forward to the clitic or backward to an inflectional prefix
- prepositions /ba/ 'with', /bɛ/ 'to', /æz/ 'from' trigger vowel harmony on clitics which attach to them enclitically
[h]-insertion between the final V of the preposition and the initial V of the enclitic
ex.: ba+æm -> baham 'with me'
be+æm -> behem 'to me'
æz+ɛf -> æzæf 'from her/ him'
- negative prefix /næ-/ , subjunctive/ imperative prefix /be-/ undergo V-harmony to assimilate to the V in the following morpheme:
/be-/ > [bo-]
/næ-/ only assimilates to the durative prefix /mi-/
næ-xord [næxord] 'he/ she didn't eat'
næ-mi-xord [nemixord] 'he/ she doesn't eat'
- in a number of verbs the harmony is optionally

4. Stress

- not phonemic
- 2 levels: weak, strong
- one strong stress per word
- syllables get different pitch levels within the word, but pitch assignment is more phrase-sensitive
- stress is assigned at word level and is generally being kept in combining words to larger phrases, but there are interactions
- shifting of stress is possible for contrasting certain information
- general rule: stress falls on the final syllable in a word (simple & derived nouns, adjectives, infinitives, plural marked nouns, compound nouns & adjectives)
ex.: ju.jé 'chicken'
æsb.á 'horse-PL'

ʃi.ri.ní	'cookie' (derived noun)
tæx.tɛ.xáb	'bed' (compound noun, structure is not clear)
xoʃ.gél	'pretty'
Gæm.gín	'sorrowful' (derived adjective)
ba.sæ.fá	'pleasant'

- exceptions: mostly in multimorphemic words
strong stress is regularly assigned to the last non-enclitic/ non-inflectional syllable of the word

1) suffixes which do not take stress, e.g. pronominal clitics, ezafe, indefinite marker

--> stress on the penultimate syllable

ex.: maʃín-æm	'my car'
car -1sg	
tú-ye	'in'
in-EZ	
æk.s-i	'a picture'
picture-IND	

2) durative prefix /mi-/, negative prefix /næ-/, subjunctive/ imperative prefix /be-/ attract primary stress from the verbal root when they occur as first syllable of the word

ex.: mí -xun-æm
DUR-read-1sg
'I am reading'

3) stress lexically assigned: not finally

ex.: bæɛ	'yes'
ʃayæd	'possibly'

5. Assimilatory Processes

5a) Velarization, Uvularization

- /n/ velarizes before /k/, /g/ and uvularizes before /G/
ex.: [ræŋg] 'color'
[ɛNGæd] 'this amount' (morphological structure not clear, DEM is in-/ un-)

it seems to occur also intermorphemic

5b) Labialization

- /n/ labializes before /b/ and /p/
 ex.: /ænb̥ar/ > [æmbar] 'amber'
 /dɒnb̥al/ > [dombal] 'following'
 /in pænir/ > [impænir] 'this cheese'
 DEMcheese
- /n/ assimilates before /f/, /v/ and becomes either labial or labial-dental
 ex.: /ænv̥a/ > [æmva] 'variety'

5c) Devoicing

- voiced stops partially devoice after a voiceless segment within a word and word-finally
 ex.: /xub/ > [xup] 'good'
 /ʃɒs-dæn/ > [ʃɒstæn] 'to wash'
 wash-INF

5d) Spirantization

- G often spirantizes between sonorants within a word
 examples only monomorphemic: /aGa/ > [aʒa] 'sir, man'
- in some cases additional devoicing of /G/:
 /ræGs/ > [ræxs] 'dance'

5e) Total Assimilation

- sometimes occur when /s/ is preceded by /t/
 ex.: /bæstɛ/ > [bæssɛ] 'package'

6. Dissimilation

- Affricate /dʒ/ sometimes spirantizes: occlusive becomes fricative before another occlusive
 ex.: /ɛdʒtɛma/ > [ɛʒtɛma] 'society'
 /ɛdʒbar/ > [ɛʒbar] 'obligation'
- affricate /tʃ/ spirantizes before /k/
 ex.: hitʃki/ > [hiʃki] 'no one'

7. a-/ u-alternation

- /a/ becomes [u] before /n/ or /m/ within a word
 ex.: /an/ > [ʔun] 'this'

/mæn-dæn/ > [mʌndæən] 'to remain'

remain-INF

/nɛgær-an/ > [nɛgærən] 'worried'

worry-PRES.PART

- there are exceptions

8. Deletion

8a) h-deletion

- most often deleted in clusters, word-finally, intervocalically
- not obligatory
- compensatory lengthening of the V when /h/ is deleted between V and C

- in clusters:
 - deleted in medial and final clusters
 - exceptions!
 - ex.: /jæhr/ > [jæ:r]'city'
 - /sobh/ > [sob] 'morning'
 - /ɛhtɛram/ > [ɛ:tɛram] 'respect'
 - /sæfhɛ/ > [sæfɛ] 'page'

- word-finally:
 - not deleted in derived and inflected forms when the morpheme following the stem ending in /h/ begins with a V
 - ex.: /dæh/ > [dæ] 'ten'
 - /dæh-omin/ > [dæhomin] 'tenth'
 - ten-ORD

- intervocalically:
 - only few words
 - ex.: /xahɛf/ > [xæf]'request'
 - only few words in which both, the /h/ and the following V are deleted
 - ex.: /tʃahar/ > [tʃar] 'four'

- only 1 case, where /h/ deleted in syllable-initial position: when the unstressed enclitic /-hæm/ 'also' is added to a stem ending in a C, the /h/ of the enclitic is deleted
 - ex.: /mæn-hæm/ > [mænæm] 'I also'

8b) Glottal Stop Deletion

- in C-clusters:

- wether word-final or word-medial
 - wether it is the first or second element
 - when /r/ is the first element after a V, that V undergoes lengthening
- ex.: /dʒæmʔ/ > [dʒæm] 'crowd'
- /bæʔd/ > [bæ:d] 'after'
- word-finally:
 - preceding V lengthened

ex.: /noʔ/ > [no:] 'kind, sort'
 - intervocalic:
 - no lengthening

ex.: /saʔæt/ > [saæt] 'hour'

/tæbiʔ-i/ > [tæbii] 'natural'

nature-ATTR

8c) r-deletion

- in a limited number of words /r/ is deleted as second element of a word-final cluster
- ex.: /fɛkr/ > [fɛk] 'thought'
- in word-final /hr/-clusters, it is always the /h/ which is deleted

8d) t-deletion

- /t/ deleted as second element of the clusters /st/, /ft/ followed by a V
- ex.: /dæst/ > [dæs] 'hand'
- /dæstgah/ > [dæsgah] 'equipment'

8d) d-deletion

- possible in word-final position following /n/
- ex.: /mund-ænd/ > [mundæn] 'they stayed'
- stay -3pl
- other instances occur only across morpheme boundaries when the morpheme following the cluster begins with a C
- ex.: /tʃænd-ta/ > [tʃænta] 'how many'
- how many-CLASS

8e) V-deletion

- when a pronominal clitic beginning with a V attaches to either a nominal stem or a preposition or when a AGR marker is suffixed to a verbal root, the initial V is deleted

- ex.: /ʃirini=et/ > [ʃirinit] 'your cookie'
cookie=2sg
- /ba=ɛʃ/ > [baʃ] 'with him'
with=3sg
- /mi-xa-æm/ > [mixam] 'I want'
DUR-want-1sg

9. Insertion

9a) ʔ-insertion

- ʔ inserted before a V at the beginning of a breath group
- ex.: /in/ > [ʔin] 'this'
- /æks/ > [ʔæks] 'photograph'
- when these two words are combined within a breath group, the non-initial word loses its prevocalic ʔ
[ʔinæks] 'this photograph'

9b) ε-insertion

- inserted between a stem ending in C and a plural pronominal clitic
- ex.: /mænzɛl-mun/ > [mænzɛlɛmun] 'our house'
house-1pl
- C clusters preceded by /a, /i/ or /u/ (these vowels are always long) or a diphthong may be broken up with an epenthetic /ɛ/
ex.: /aftab/ > [afɛtab] 'sun'

9c) Glide-insertion y

- between long V (a, i, u) and a following V
- across morpheme boundaries
- ex.: /ketab-ha-æm/ > [ketabayæm] 'my books'
book-PL-1sg

9d) h-insertion

- only prepositional clitic forms involved
- inserted between V of the prepositional stem and the V of the clitic
- ex.: /ba-æm/ > [baham] 'with me'
with-1sg
- exceptions: never, when a mid-vowel is followed by any other vowel
ex.: /to-i/ > [toi] 'it is you'

10. Reduplication

- partial: nouns, very productive, indicates plurality and intensification
 - result in a rhyming compound whereby the second part is a nonsense word formed by replacing the initial C of the first word with /m/ or /p/
ex.: [tʃiz] 'thing' > [tʃizmiz] 'things'
- total: used to make adverbs (intensification)
 - also present participles can be reduplicated to produce intensified adverbs
ex.: dœvan dœvan 'running, running'

11. Compounds

- considered one "word"
- the last non-enclitic syllable of the compound gets stress

12. "Clitics"

- pronominal clitics:
 - in compound verbs the clitic may be either suffixed to the first element or placed after the verbal inflections
ex.: komæk=ɛf--kærd-æm
help-3sg--did-1sg
'I helped her/ him'

komæk--kærd-æm=ɛf
help--did-1sg-3sg
'I helped her/ him'
 - these clitics also attach to nouns (possession, copulative sense), prepositions
 - unstressed
- connectives:
 - /-o/ 'and', /-(h)æm/ 'also'
mæn=o to
I=and you
'you and me'

mæn=æm mi-ya-m
I=also DUR-come-1sg

'I'll come too'

- /o/ can attach to clauses to form coordinated sentences, it attaches generally to the inflected verb

mæn bala-ro tæmiz--mi-kon-æm=o ʃirin pain-o morætæb--mi-kon-ε
I upstairs-OBJ clean--DUR-do-1sg=and Shirin downstairs-OBJ neat--DUR-
do-3s

'I'll clean upstairs and Shirin will straighten up downstairs'